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EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT- A PATHWAY TO SUCCESS

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Abstract

Organizations expect the employees to believe in its mission, purpose and values and come out with the commitment by way of their deeds. This situation is called Employee Engagement. An employee, who has total belief in the organization, has a desire to work to make things better and better in the business context, he is considered to be an Engaged Employee. They put forth an extra effort, as well as are very loyal towards their organization. They work there for long and show a strong level of commitment. Employee Engagement is a powerful source of competitive advantage. With this a research study was conducted among the employees of a reputed industrial organization at Hosur. A proper methodology was followed, tool administered, statistical test were done and findings were drawn.

Introduction:

Employee Engagement is the degree to which an employee is emotionally bonded to his/her organization and passionate about his/her work. Employee Engagement essentially depicts our connection to our work, our organization, our customers, our effects and to results. In any study involving employee engagement the three aspects which are studied are: i. Employees as unique entities in terms of their skills, abilities, attitudes and aspirations., ii. Employee in their role to create conditions of engagement and iii. Relationship, trust and communication between employees across levels. The challenge is not only to attract the best talent but also to engage the employees like, raising opportunities for carrier development, life style decisions, job changing and unbalanced work life which influence an individual's decision to continue or quite.

“Engagement is the process in which the employees are encouraged to engage with the organization for the maximum period of time or until the completion of the project

Definition:

According to, Employee Engagement is “the harnessing of organisation members’ selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances”(Kahn ,1990). Miles (2001) says that EE means to intensively involve all employees in high-engagement cascades that create understanding, dialogue, feedback and accountability. According to Daniel (2004), EE is a positive, two-way relationship between employee and his organization where both parties are aware of their own and the other's needs, and support each other to fulfill these needs and go the extra mile, and both reap mutual benefits. Lanphear (2004), too is of the same opinion that EE as the bond employees have with their organization. When these committed employees really care about the

business, they are more likely to go an extra mile. Thus Employee Engagement can be understood as the degree to which an employee is emotionally bonded to his/her organisation and is passionate about the work that really matters. It also explains the extent to which people enjoy and believe in what they do and feel valued for doing it.

Hence, Employee engagement is a property of the relationship between an organization and its employees. When employees find the physical work place and especially the psychological work environment (organizational culture) to their liking, they form a positive *emotional connection* which makes them much more likely to "go the extra mile" and commit enthusiastically to their own job and their role at the organization. The *choices and action* which this heightened positive emotional state can bring about are called "engagement".

The Study on Employee Engagement

The research was done based on the topic "Employee Engagement" at a reputed manufacturing Organization situated in Hosur, the industrial town of Tamilnadu. Here the researcher wanted to study about the level of employee engagement in an organization. During past two decades, employee engagement became a very popular managerial concept. Organizations use different engagement building tools in order to stay competitive and improve performance. The aim of this paper is to contribute to the research regarding the engagement of employees within its organization, though their day-to-day performance has a significant influence on the quality of the entire institution performance. This paper will apply related concepts, theories and critics and engagement measuring methods to measure the existing level of engagement of the employees in an industry.

Objectives:

The aim in this research was to find the current engagement level of employees and to find the factors, which need to be improved in order to further increase engagement. This study was conducted to study the passion, work life, commitment and involvement of the employees, employee potentiality, job satisfaction, employees' leadership and management support in the organization.

Methodology:

The research was also supported with the information from the review of literature from books, journals and articles. The researcher used the Descriptive design for this research to describe about the various factors of Employee Engagement. The samples were chosen by stratified disproportionate simple random sampling using lottery method. The total number of samples was 100. Questionnaire consisting of 54 questions under employee engagement in various factors was used to collect data. The collected data was analyzed and interpretation was done and the outcome has been represented through tables and chi square test was used to test the hypothesis.

Major Findings:

1. The analyzed data shows that half (50%) of the respondents really looked forward to going to work always and also the respondents were very passionate in doing work happily.
2. The data explains that two third (66%) of the respondents agreed that their job activities were personally meaningful.

3. There is no significant relationship between marital status and achieved correct balance between home and work lives. So null hypothesis (H0) is accepted and alternative (H1) hypothesis is rejected. It is presented below:

Table – 1

Marital Status * Achieve the correct balance between home and Work Lives

Marital Status	Achieve the correct balance between home and Work Lives		Total
	Agree	Disagree	
Single	27(84.4) (32.1)	5(15.6) (31.2)	32(100.0) (32.0)
Married	57(83.8) (67.9)	11(16.2) (68.8)	68(100.0) (68.0)
Total	84(84.0) (100.0)	16(16.0) (100.0)	100(100.0) (100.0)

4. It is found that more than two third (70%) of the respondents have said the present working job was mildly stressful.
5. The analyzed data described that the majority (83%) of the respondents were always providing heart full commitment on their work.
6. “Loyalty in and of itself will not solve a company’s challenges, but strong employee loyalty will put the company in a better position to face them.” Loyalty is built upon trust and without it there can be no loyalty. The surest sign of trust is to give the employees to power to make decisions to do the right thing. If that trust is granted, it is amazing how closely loyalty follows. The below table shows about the employees level of loyalty towards organization, supervisor, manager, and co-workers in an industry.

Table – 2

Employees Level of Loyalty in an Industry

Employees Level of Loyalty	Loyalty towards Organization	Loyalty towards Supervisor	Loyalty towards Manager	Loyalty towards Co-worker
Very High	63(63.0)	10(10.0)	17(17.0)	33(33.0)
High	28(28.0)	69(69.0)	52(52.0)	46(46.0)
Low	9(9.0)	15(15.0)	26(26.0)	13(13.0)
Very Low	0(0)	6(6.0)	5(5.0)	8(8.0)
Total	100(100.0)	100(100.0)	100(100.0)	100(100.0)

It is encouraging to see that the majority is less than two third (63%) of the respondents showed their level of loyalty is very high towards organization, and more than two third (69%) of the respondents showed their level of loyalty is high towards supervisor. The table shows more than half (52%) of the respondents have said their level of loyalty towards manager is high and again the highest is less than half (46%) of the respondents showed their level of loyalty towards co-workers.

Finally it can be inferred that the overall assessment says the respondents have showed either very high or high level of loyalty towards their organization, supervisor, manager and co-workers.

7. Little more than half (51%) of the respondents were always exerting a lot of energy for better performance.
8. The data enumerates that little less than half (47%) of the respondents said that they used to stay always until the job was done in the organization.
9. It was found that more than half (56%) of the respondents always get excited when they were performing well in their job.
10. The collected data states that less than half (43%) of the respondents agreed with their current salary and remuneration.
11. Less than two third (63%) of the respondents agreed that they have cordial and friendly relationship between employees and managers.
12. The data states that less than half (42%) of the respondents said that sometimes the management treats the employees fairly.
13. Exactly half (50%) of the respondents have said that their business unit keeps them fully informed about the happenings in their department and in the organization.
14. More than half (54%) of the respondents agreed that they had plan to remain with the same organization for the foreseeable future.
15. The response for the question for what reason they had intended to leave the job in the last one year is given below:

Table – 3
Reasons for intending to leave job within a year

Reasons for Leaving Job	Yes
Intend to find another similar Job	12(12.0)
Intend to do a different type of Work	15(15.0)
Intend to be Self-Employed	20(20.0)
Intend to Retire Voluntarily	11(11.0)
Intend to return to full time Study	6(6.0)
Intend to care for your Children	5(5.0)
Intend to care for other Dependents	7(7.0)
Intend to leave for low Job Satisfaction	-
No Better pay/benefits elsewhere	18(18.0)
No Opportunities for Promotion	22(22.0)
Easier/Shorter Journey to Work	1(1.0)
No More Flexible Working Hours	8(8.0)
Other Reason	4(4.0)

The first highest is more than one fifth (22%) of the respondents said that there was no opportunity for promotion. The second highest is exactly one fifth (20%) of the respondents said that they would intend to leave the organization for the purpose of Self-Employment The next is less than one fifth (18%) of the respondents said that they leave their job for the purpose of no better pay/benefits ,and finally the table clearly shows that all the 100 respondents would not leave the organization for the purpose of low job Satisfaction, and clearly says that all the employees in the organization are satisfied with their present job in the organization.

